

Euphorbia radyeri Blounoorsdoring

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 1 m

Distribution:

Euphorbia radyeri (syn. *Euphorbia caerulescens*), grows on stony slopes and flats among arid scrub and larger bushes from Calitzdorp to Klipplaat and Jansenville.

Importance:

The blounoorsdoring, blue euphorbia in English, is a drought-tolerant succulent valued in ornamental horticulture for water-wise gardens. Its stems can be used as emergency livestock fodder after the latex has dried to reduce toxicity. The species itself is not currently threatened, but many southern African *Euphorbia* species face pressure from illegal collection and habitat loss, underscoring the importance of ecological research and conservation planning.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 202.22 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 13.44 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 5.77 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 7.5%, Duplicated: 92.0%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 12 527.56 kilobases

Contig number: 2 263

Sample Contributor contact details:

Mr Thabang Makola

South African National Biodiversity Institute

T.makola@sanbi.org.za

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